

Supporting Information

MCF Classifier: estimating, standardising, and stratifying medicine carbon footprints, at scale

Haroon Taylor¹, Shazia Mahamdallie¹, Matthew Sawyer², Nazneen Rahman¹

¹YewMaker, London, UK

²SEE Sustainability, Leeming Bar, North Yorkshire, UK

Correspondence to: Nazneen Rahman nazneen@yewmaker.com

Contents

Supplementary Methods.....	2
Model Evaluation Criteria.....	2
Models Evaluated.....	3
References.....	6

Supplementary Methods

Model Evaluation Criteria

All the models assessed for use in the MCF Method pipeline were evaluated qualitatively by the following criteria:

- **Fidelity:** How well does the model represent the real life property or metric that is being predicted?
- **Accuracy:** How well can the model estimate the outcome variable we are trying to predict?
- **Extensibility:** How well can the model be applied to circumstances beyond the specific set it was trained on? This was important because of the limited size and breadth of datasets available.
- **Scalability:** How easily can the model be scaled to apply to thousands of medicine products?
- **Accessibility:** Can the input variables of the model be extracted and verified automatically.
- **Simplicity:** How easy is the model to understand? We follow Occam's razor - where two models are similar in other areas choose the simpler model. An open source model is considered easier to understand and therefore simpler.
- **Reproducibility and Standardisation:** How comparable are results produced by the model?

We first focused on evaluating methods to predict Global Warming Potential (GWP) values (Step 7) to establish a standardised metric, which could be converted to gCO₂e per dose using dose information (Step 8). We then systematically evaluated each preceding step that involved modelling (Steps 6, 3, and 4) to ensure it met our criteria for fidelity, accuracy, extensibility, scalability, accessibility, simplicity, and reproducibility. Steps involving empirical data (Steps 1, 2, 5, 8) were integrated directly.

Model Evaluations

Predicting GWP (Step 7)

The aim of this step was to calculate the outcome variable of Global Warming Potential using existing metrics that are regularly calculated in process chemistry. Three approaches were evaluated:

- **E factor**

- The E factor, developed in 1992¹, is a measure of the waste generated by a chemical process and was one of the first sustainability based metrics used in process chemistry that assesses a chemical process using a metric other than yield.²
- In its simplest form it is defined by the equation:
 - $$E = \frac{\text{kg waste}}{\text{kg product}}$$
- Decisions of the system boundaries and what is considered “waste” are important considerations for E factor calculations.
- Assessments that take into account all process materials including solvents and water are often referred to as the complete E factor (cEF).³
- A higher E factor indicates a more inefficient process.
- A E factor of zero indicates a perfectly efficient process with no waste.

- **Process Mass Intensity (PMI)**

- Process Mass Intensity is another mass based measure of the efficiency of a chemical process.
- In its simplest form it is defined by the equation:
 - $$PMI = \frac{\text{kg input materials}}{\text{kg product}} = E \text{ factor} + 1$$
- However, because PMI defines the numerator as all input materials instead of waste materials (as in E factor) there is no longer a boundary definition question about what is included as “waste”.⁴
- Water and solvents are included by default in the PMI system.
- A higher PMI indicates a more environmentally “intensive” process.
- A PMI of one indicates a perfectly efficient process with no waste.

- **Relative process greenness (RPG)**

- Relative process greenness extends the concept of the complete E factor by comparing it to an average or expected value.⁵
- In its simplest form it is defined by the equations:
 - $$iGAL = 0.403 \times \text{functional molecular weight}$$
 - $$RPG = iGAL/cEF \times 100$$
- RPG is given as a percentage where 100% can be viewed as a process that is as wasteful as expected. Greater than 100% is a process that is less wasteful than expected. Lower than 100% is a process that is more wasteful than expected.

All three metrics exhibit an intuitive relationship with global warming potential (**similar fidelity**). However, only Process Mass Intensity (PMI) demonstrated a quantitative linear relationship ($R^2 = 0.878$) as reported in the literature (**higher accuracy**).⁴

Empirical calculation of these metrics at scale is impractical because it requires comprehensive knowledge of each medicine's processing steps (**poor reproducibility, accessibility, and scalability**).

The more extensive research and multiple models for predicting PMI suggest the accuracy and fidelity of PMI predictions are likely superior to those for RPG and E-factor. Moreover, the added complexity of RPG did not provide a significant advantage in the evaluated criteria. Therefore, PMI was chosen as the most suitable metric for predicting GWP, due to its superior accuracy, scalability, and simplicity.

Predicting PMI (Step 6)

After selecting PMI as the most suitable predictor of GWP, the best way to predict or measure PMI was next assessed. Three approaches were evaluated:

- **Calculate PMI from first principles** (empirically)

As PMI is defined as the amount of input materials (kg) divided by the amount of API produced (kg), it can theoretically be calculated empirically with comprehensive knowledge of the full manufacturing steps. However, this information is proprietary and typically held by manufacturers, making it inaccessible (**low reproducibility**). Additionally, even if the information could be retrieved, calculating PMI empirically at scale would be impractical due to the variability in data formats and storage locations across numerous pharmaceutical companies (**low scalability**).

- **PMI Predictor**⁶

The PMI Predictor estimates PMI in silico based on the synthesis steps and the molecules involved, without the need to perform the synthesis route or determine specific yields and inputs. However, the approach still requires detailed knowledge of the synthesis steps, which is often inaccessible or only available from outdated patents (**low reproducibility and low scalability**). Furthermore, the PMI Predictor requires extensive knowledge of chemical processes to use and interpret (**low simplicity**).

- **SMART-PMI**⁷

SMART-PMI predicts PMI from the molecular structure of the API, which is known and publicly available (**high reproducibility and high scalability**). When compared to the minimum synthetic PMI for 30 compounds SMART-PMI demonstrated a reasonable correlation (**acceptable accuracy**). The model was trained using molecules from various development phases (1,2,3 & commercial) (**good extensibility**). Additionally, the linear model relies on only two input variables—synthetic complexity and molecular weight (**high simplicity**).

SMART-PMI was selected as the most suitable method for predicting PMI due to its high reproducibility, scalability, and simplicity. It clearly outperformed the other evaluated methods.

Predicting Complexity (Steps 3 & 4)

The two input variables of the SMART-PMI model are molecular weight and synthetic complexity. Molecular weight is an empirical value accessible for any small molecule⁸, synthetic complexity requires modelling. We evaluated five models.

- **Molecular weight**

Using only molecular weight would have **high simplicity, high scalability, high extensibility, and high reproducibility**. However, molecules with similar molecular weights often have substantially different structures, complexity, and synthetic pathways resulting in limited correlation with complexity models (**low fidelity, low accuracy**).

- **MeanComplexity⁹**

SMART-PMI has an internal model for synthetic complexity called the meanComplexity, but it relies on elements that are not open source (**low reproducibility**) and not easy to automate (**average scalability**).

- **Complexity-based metric¹⁰**

This model, by Kjell et al, predicts PMI directly using characteristics such as the number of chiral centres and heteroatoms. The model is fully automatable as its input variables are empirical characteristics of the molecule (**high scalability**). However it was trained with only 14 molecules, with very low correlation when tested against commercial products (**low extensibility**).¹⁰ The model showed a moderate correlation to meanComplexity (R-Squared = 0.59) (**moderate accuracy**).⁹

- **SCScore¹¹**

This machine learning model assumes that products of chemical reactions are more complicated than their corresponding reagents (**high fidelity**). It is based on 12 million reactions (**high extensibility**) and is fully open source (**high reproducibility**). However, there is no available correlation with meanComplexity or confirmed utility in PMI prediction (**unknown accuracy**).

- **SAScore¹²**

The SAScore measures the synthetic accessibility of a molecule (i.e. how easy it is to synthesise), considering many molecular characteristics (**high fidelity**). It is based on 1 million molecules (**high extensibility**), is fully automatable (**high scalability**) and fully open source (**high reproducibility**). It has a high correlation with meanComplexity score (R-Squared = 0.89; **high accuracy**).⁹

SAScore was chosen for its close correlation with meanComplexity, ease of use, simplicity, fidelity, accuracy, and scalability. Whilst SCScore was trained on a larger dataset it could not be used to predict either meanComplexity or PMI directly without the creation and validation of a new model. Additionally, recent research has shown that synthetic accessibility scores incorporating human-determined features and input variables (like SAScore) outperform pure machine learning techniques which are often prone to overfitting.¹³

References

1. Sheldon RA. Organic synthesis-past, present and future. *Chem Ind.* 1992;23:903–6.
2. Arthur Sheldon R. The E factor at 30: a passion for pollution prevention. *Green Chem.* 2023;25(5):1704–28.
3. A. Sheldon R. The E factor 25 years on: the rise of green chemistry and sustainability. *Green Chem.* 2017;19(1):18–43.
4. Jimenez-Gonzalez C, Ponder CS, Broxterman QB, Manley JB. Using the Right Green Yardstick: Why Process Mass Intensity Is Used in the Pharmaceutical Industry To Drive More Sustainable Processes. *Org Process Res Dev.* 2011 Jul 15;15(4):912–7.
5. Roschangar F, Li J, Zhou Y, Aelterman W, Borovika A, Colberg J, et al. Improved iGAL 2.0 Metric Empowers Pharmaceutical Scientists to Make Meaningful Contributions to United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 12. *ACS Sustain Chem Eng.* 2022 Apr 25;10(16):5148–62.
6. Borovika A, Albrecht J, Li J, Wells AS, Briddell C, Dillon BR, et al. The PMI Predictor app to enable green-by-design chemical synthesis. *Nat Sustain.* 2019 Nov;2(11):1034–40.
7. Sherer EC, Bagchi A, Kosjek B, Maloney KM, Peng Z, Robaire SA, et al. Driving Aspirational Process Mass Intensity Using Simple Structure-Based Prediction. *Org Process Res Dev.* 2022 May 20;26(5):1405–10.
8. Kim S, Chen J, Cheng T, Gindulyte A, He J, He S, et al. PubChem 2023 update. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2023 Jan 6;51(D1):D1373–80.
9. Sheridan RP, Zorn N, Sherer EC, Campeau LC, Chang C (Zhenyu), Cumming J, et al. Modeling a Crowdsourced Definition of Molecular Complexity. *J Chem Inf Model.* 2014 Jun 23;54(6):1604–16.
10. Kjell DP, Watson IA, Wolfe CN, Spitler JT. Complexity-Based Metric for Process Mass Intensity in the Pharmaceutical Industry. *Org Process Res Dev.* 2013 Feb 15;17(2):169–74.
11. Coley CW, Rogers L, Green WH, Jensen KF. SCScore: Synthetic Complexity Learned from a Reaction Corpus. *J Chem Inf Model.* 2018 Feb 26;58(2):252–61.
12. Ertl P, Schuffenhauer A. Estimation of synthetic accessibility score of drug-like molecules based on molecular complexity and fragment contributions. *J Cheminformatics.* 2009 Jun 10;1(1):8.
13. Skoraczyński G, Kitlas M, Miasojedow B, Gambin A. Critical assessment of synthetic accessibility scores in computer-assisted synthesis planning. *J Cheminformatics.* 2023 Jan 14;15(1):6.